

Treatment of Batteries Waste by using Steriliser Production Device

**Ali Kareem Shabath, Abbas Mustafa Mohammed Ali, Mortada Sareh Mkhayfi,
Ghasaq Hasan Jasim**

Department of Environmental pollution, College of Science, University of Al-Qasim Green

Ahmed Emad Milli Hamidan, Riyad Saud Hadi

Department of Environment, College of Science, University of Al-Qasim Green

Abstract:

In this research, we study the design of a device that produces sterilizers that are produced by preparing chlorine and hydrogen gas from potassium chloride and water in the presence of sodium hydroxide by electrolysis through a continuous electric current to the graphite electrodes, the anode, and cathode electrodes. These sterilizers are compounds (Sodium hypochlorite, potassium chlorite, potassium permanganate).

Disadvantages	Advantages
1. The electrodes are corroded, Therefore, it is better to use electrodes that resist corrosion such as titanium.	1. Simple and inexpensive technique and can be relied upon.
2. It does not affect some parasites like Giardia, Cryptosporidium, and worm eggs.	2. Effectively kills bacteria and viruses.
3. The dosage should be carefully determined.	3. Residual chlorine provides some protection against recontamination.
4. It requires clear water to be more efficient	4. Easy to operate
5. Chlorination of water with high organic matter leads to the risk of the formation of toxic side disinfection products.	5. Non-toxic and non-hazardous material.
	6. Not waste.

The students' successful learning experience primarily depends on the academic delivery and educational programs implemented by institutions as part of their main task in the public service under the educational sector. However, in public service in the academe, all aspects of services rendered should be reasonably considered including all administrative offices. While teachers in classrooms are responsible for student growth, administrative offices take charge of the governance of resources and public affairs. In the context of the Philippine government, the highest ethical standards are embodied in Republic Act No. 6713 otherwise known as the Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards for Public Officials and Employees. It embodies eight (8) norms of conduct including professionalism, commitment to the public interest, justness and sincerity, political neutrality, responsiveness, nationalism and patriotism, democracy commitment, and modesty in living. Demands for the need to improve public service during the COVID 19 pandemic drastically increased. Improvements to the systems of operation in government offices were forced for its operation to continue without compromising the safety of everyone. Whereas new ideas in rendering services have been tested for effectiveness and reliability to comply with the demands in public service amidst pandemics. Education is one of the highly challenged sectors in the Philippines at this time. As public health safety versus continuous education is debated, the authorities did not stop finding ways for education to continue without compromising public health safety. The academe continued while administrative services strived harder to expose themselves to danger while experimenting with which processes and systems will apply to them. Office of the Registrars served as the frontline of schools in monitoring the enrollment and managing various school records. While its operation has been affected and limited by the global health threat, these offices need to continue their services with their stakeholders at full potential even without face-to-face transactions. Thus, the Office of the Registrar's transactions should remain integrity and confidential while it remains available anytime and anywhere. Office of the Registrars particularly in schools in the City of San Jose del Monte is currently facing never experienced challenges. To cope with these challenges, they need to grab the opportunities that technology can offer and test some innovations which are not only in response to the global threat challenges but as well as the future may demand.